

On Suborbital Graphs of the Congruence Subgroup $\Gamma_0(N)$

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Abstract—In this paper we examine some properties of suborbital graphs for the congruence subgroup $\Gamma_0(N)$. Then we give necessary and sufficient conditions for graphs to have triangels.

Keywords—Congruence subgroup, Imprimitve action, Modular group, Suborbital graphs.

I. INTRODUCTION

LET Γ denote the inhomogeneous group $\text{PSL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$ acting on the upper half plane $H := \{z \in \mathbb{C} : \text{Im}(z) > 0\}$ via:

$$A(z) = \frac{az + b}{cz + d}, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma.$$

Among the subgroups of Γ the congruence subgroups such as

$$\Gamma(N) := \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma \mid a \equiv d \equiv 1 \pmod{N}, b \equiv c \equiv 0 \pmod{N} \right\}$$

$$\Gamma_0(N) := \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma \mid c \equiv 0 \pmod{N} \right\}$$

have been the objects of detailed studies due to their signifiante in the arithmetic of elliptic curves, integral quadratic forms, elliptic modular forms in [5], [6]. In this paper, we define $\Gamma^*(N)$ as the group obtained by adding the stabilizer of ∞ to the congruence subgroup $\Gamma(N)$, that is,

$$\Gamma^*(N) := \left\langle \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \Gamma(N) \right\rangle$$

which is easily seen that

$$\Gamma^*(N) = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1+aN & b \\ cN & 1+dN \end{pmatrix} : a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}, \det = 1 \right\}.$$

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II. THE ACTION OF $\Gamma_0(N)$ ON $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}$

Every element of $\hat{\mathbb{Q}} := \mathbb{Q} \cup \{\infty\}$ can be represented as a reduced fraction $\frac{x}{y}$, with $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(x, y) = 1$. Since

$\frac{x}{y} = \frac{-x}{-y}$, this representation is not unique. We represent ∞ as

$\frac{1}{0} = \frac{-1}{0}$. The action of the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma$ on $\frac{x}{y}$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} : \frac{x}{y} \rightarrow \frac{ax+by}{cx+dy}.$$

It is easily seen that if $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma$ and $\frac{x}{y} \in \hat{\mathbb{Q}}$ is a reduced fraction then, since $c(ax+by) - a(cx+dy) = -y$ and $d(ax+by) - b(cx+dy) = x$,

$$(ax+by, cx+dy) = 1.$$

The action of a matrix on $\frac{x}{y}$ and on $\frac{-x}{-y}$ is identical.

Theorem 2.1. The action of $\Gamma_0(N)$ on $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}$ is not transitive.

Proof. From (1), for $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ cN & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma_0(N)$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ cN & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ N \end{pmatrix} = \frac{a+bN}{cN+dN}$$

is a reduced fraction, so $\frac{1}{N}$ is not sent to $\frac{1}{N+1}$ under the action of $\Gamma_0(N)$.

Without loss of generality, for making calculations easier, N will be a prime p throughout the paper.

Theorem 2.2. The orbits of $\Gamma_0(p)$ are $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$ and $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$.

Proof. Using the corollaries from [2] we can write down the sets of orbits of $\Gamma_0(N)$ in general

$$\begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \end{pmatrix} = \left\{ \frac{x}{y} \in \hat{\mathbb{Q}} : (p, y) = b, x \equiv a \pmod{\left(b, \frac{N}{b}\right)} \right\}.$$

Then we have

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix} = \left\{ \frac{k}{yp} : k \in \mathbb{Z}, (k, yp) = 1 \right\}$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \left\{ \frac{k}{\ell} : k, \ell \in \mathbb{Z}, (k, \ell) = 1 \right\}.$$

We now consider the imprimitivity of the action of $\Gamma_0(p)$ on $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}$.

Let (G, Ω) be transitive permutation group, consisting of a group G acting on a set Ω transitively. An equivalence relation $\approx$ on Ω is called G -invariant if whenever $\alpha, \beta \in \Omega$ satisfy $\alpha \approx \beta$ then $g(\alpha) \approx g(\beta)$ for all g in G . The equivalence classes are called blocks.

We call (G, Ω) imprimitive if Ω admits some G -invariant equivalence relation different from

- (i) the identity relation, $\alpha \approx \beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$
- (ii) the universal relation, $\alpha \approx \beta$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Omega$.

Otherwise (G, Ω) is called primitive. We now give a lemma from [3].

Lemma 2.3. Let (G, Ω) be transitive. (G, Ω) imprimitive if and only if G_α , the stabilizer of a point $\alpha \in \Omega$, is a maximal subgroup of G for each $\alpha \in \Omega$.

What the lemma is saying is whenever $G_\alpha \leq H \leq G$, then Ω admits some G -invariant equivalence relation other than trivial cases. In fact, since G acts transitively, every element of Ω has the form $g(\alpha)$ for some $g \in G$. If we define the relation $\approx$ on Ω as

$$g(\alpha) \approx g'(\alpha) \text{ if and only if } g' \in gH,$$

then it is easily seen that it is non-trivial G -invariant equivalence relation. That is (G, Ω) imprimitive.

From the above we see that the number of blocks is equal to the index $|G : H|$.

We now apply these ideas to the case where G is the $\Gamma_0(p)$ and Ω is $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}$. An obvious choice for H is $\Gamma^*(p)$. Clearly $\Gamma_\infty \leq \Gamma^*(p) \leq \Gamma_0(p)$. Then we have

Corollary 2.4. $(\Gamma_0(p), \hat{\mathbb{Q}})$ is imprimitive permutation group.

$\Gamma_0(p)$ acts transitively and imprimitively on the set $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$.

Let $\approx$ denote the $\Gamma_0(p)$ -invariant equivalence relation induced on $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$ by $\Gamma_0(p)$ as:

If $v = \frac{a_1}{pc_1}$ and $w = \frac{a_2}{pc_2}$ are elements of $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$, then $v = g(\infty)$ and $w = g'(\infty)$ for elements $g, g' \in \Gamma_0(p)$ of the form

$$g = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ pc_1 & d_1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad g' = \begin{pmatrix} a_2 & b_2 \\ pc_2 & d_2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now $v \approx w$ if and only if $g^{-1}g' \in \Gamma^*(p)$, that is,

$$g^{-1}g' = \begin{pmatrix} d_1a_2 - p(c_2b_1) & d_1b_2 - b_1d_2 \\ p(a_1c_2 - c_1a_2) & a_1d_2 - p(c_1b_2) \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma^*(p)$$

if and only if $d_1a_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ and $d_2a_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Then $a_1d_1a_2 \equiv a_1 \pmod{p}$ and so $a_1 \equiv a_2 \pmod{p}$.

Hence we see that

$$v \approx w \text{ if and only if } a_1 \equiv a_2 \pmod{p} \quad (1)$$

By our general discussion of imprimitivity, the number $\psi(p)$ of equivalence class under $\approx$ is given by

$$\psi(p) = |\Gamma_0(p) : \Gamma^*(p)|.$$

Since $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}^p \in \Gamma(p)$, then $|\Gamma^*(p) : \Gamma(p)| = p$. From [6], we know that

$$|\Gamma : \Gamma(N)| = N^3 \prod_{p|N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2}\right) \text{ and } |\Gamma : \Gamma_0(N)| = N \prod_{p|N} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right).$$

Calculating for $N = p$ and using the following equation

$$|\Gamma : \Gamma(p)| = \underbrace{|\Gamma : \Gamma_0(p)|}_{p(p^2-1)} \cdot \underbrace{|\Gamma_0(p) : \Gamma^*(p)|}_{p+1} \cdot \underbrace{|\Gamma^*(p) : \Gamma(p)|}_p,$$

we have that

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \cup \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \cup \dots \cup \begin{bmatrix} p-1 \\ p \end{bmatrix}.$$

From (1), it is clear that

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{bmatrix} = \left\{ \frac{1+xp}{yp} : x, y \in \mathbb{Z} \right\} \cong [\infty] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

III. SUBORBITAL GRAPHS

In 1967 Sims introduced the idea of suborbital graphs of a permutation group G acting on a set Ω : these are graphs with vertex set Ω , on which G induces automorphism in [7]. Also in [8] the applications are used in finite groups.

Let (G, Ω) be transitive permutation group. Then G acts on $\Omega \times \Omega$ by

$$g : (\alpha, \beta) \rightarrow (g(\alpha), g(\beta)), \quad g \in G \text{ and } \alpha, \beta \in \Omega.$$

The orbits of this action are called suborbitals of G , that containing (α, β) being denoted by $O(\alpha, \beta)$. From $O(\alpha, \beta)$ we can form a suborbital graph $G(\alpha, \beta)$: its vertices are the elements of Ω , and there is a directed edge from γ to δ , denoted by $\gamma \rightarrow \delta$, if $(\gamma, \delta) \in O(\alpha, \beta)$. We can draw this edge as a hyperbolic geodesic in the upper half-plane H .

In this final section, we determine the suborbital graphs for $\Gamma_0(p)$ on $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$. Since $\Gamma_0(p)$ acts transitively on $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$, each suborbital contains a pair (∞, v) for some $v \in \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$; $v = \frac{u}{p}$, we denote this suborbital by $O_{u,p}$ and corresponding suborbital graph by $G_{u,p}$.

$G_{u,p}$ is a disjoint union of $\psi(p)$ subgraphs forming blocks with respect to " $\approx$ " $\Gamma_0(p)$ -invariant equivalence relation. $\Gamma_0(p)$ permutes these blocks transitively and these subgraphs are all isomorphic [4].

Therefore, it is sufficient to do the calculations only for the block $[\infty]$. Let $F_{u,p}$ denote the subgraph of $G_{u,p}$ whose vertices form the block $[\infty]$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $\frac{r}{s}$ and $\frac{x}{y}$ be in the block $[\infty]$. Then there is

an edge $\frac{r}{s} \rightarrow \frac{x}{y}$ in $F_{u,p}$ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} x &\equiv \pm ur \pmod{p} \text{ and } r \equiv 1 \pmod{p}, \quad ry - sx = \pm p \\ y &\equiv \pm su \pmod{p} \text{ and } s \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \quad ry - sx = \pm p. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Since $\frac{r}{s} \rightarrow \frac{x}{y} \in F_{u,p}$, then there exists some

$T \in \Gamma^*(p)$ such that T sends the pair $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} u \\ p \end{pmatrix}$ to the pair

$$\begin{pmatrix} r \\ s \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}, \text{ that is, for } T = \begin{pmatrix} 1+ap & b \\ pc & 1+dp \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma^*(p), \det T = 1,$$

$T \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r \\ s \end{pmatrix}$ and $T \begin{pmatrix} u \\ p \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}$. From these equations, it is

clear that $x \equiv ur \pmod{p}$ and $y \equiv su \pmod{p}$.

Furthermore

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1+ap & b \\ pc & 1+dp \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & u \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r & x \\ s & y \end{pmatrix},$$

so that $ry - sx = p$.

Conversely, let be $x \equiv ur \pmod{p}$ and $y \equiv su \pmod{p}$ and also $r \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ and $s \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Then there are $b, d \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $x = ur + bp$ and $y = su + dp$. If we put these equivalences in $ry - sx = p$, we obtain

$$r(us + dp) - s(ur + bp) = p.$$

Since

$$\begin{pmatrix} r & b \\ s & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & u \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r & ur + bp \\ s & us + dp \end{pmatrix},$$

then $rd - bs = 1$. As $rd - bs \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ and $s \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, then $rd \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Since $r \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, we obtain $d \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$.

Consequently,

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} r & b \\ s & d \end{pmatrix}, \det A = 1 \text{ and } \begin{matrix} r \equiv d \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \\ s \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \end{matrix},$$

so $A \in \Gamma^*(p)$.

The proof for $(-)$ is similar.

Theorem 3.2. $\Gamma^*(p)$ permutes the vertices and the edges of $F_{u,p}$ transitively.

Proof. Suppose that $u, v \in [\infty]$. As $\Gamma_0(p)$ acts on $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ p \end{pmatrix}$

transitively, $g(u) = v$ for some $g \in \Gamma_0(p)$. Since $u \approx \infty$ and " $\approx$ " is $\Gamma_0(p)$ -invariant equivalence relation, then $g(u) \approx g(\infty)$, that is, $v \approx g(\infty)$. Thus, as $g(\infty) \in [\infty]$, $g \in \Gamma^*(p)$.

Assume that $v, w \in [\infty]$; $x, y \in [\infty]$ and $v \rightarrow w, x \rightarrow y \in F_{u,p}$. Then $(v, w) \in O_{u,p}$ and $(x, y) \in O_{u,p}$. Therefore, for some $S, T \in \Gamma_0(p)$

$$S(\infty) = v, S \begin{pmatrix} u \\ p \end{pmatrix} = w; T(\infty) = x, T(\infty) = y.$$

As $S(\infty), T(\infty) \in [\infty]$, then $S, T \in \Gamma^*(p)$. So this proof is completed.

Fig. 1 $F_{u,p}$ – Suborbital Graph

Theorem 3.3. $F_{u,p}$ contains a triangle if and only if $u^2 \pm u + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

Proof. Since $\Gamma^*(p)$ permutes the vertices transitively $F_{u,p}$ and $\infty \rightarrow \frac{u}{p}$, then we may suppose that triangle has the form

$$\infty \rightarrow \frac{u}{p} \rightarrow v \rightarrow \infty.$$

Assume that $v = \frac{x}{yp}$, $y > 0$. Since $\frac{x}{yp} \rightarrow \frac{1}{0}$, then

$$0 \cdot x - yp = \pm p.$$

As $y > 0$, then $y = 1$. Therefore $v = \frac{x}{y}$. Since $\frac{u}{p} \rightarrow \frac{x}{y}$, then

from Theorem 3.1 we obtain

$$u - x = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad x \equiv u^2 \pmod{p} \quad (2)$$

$$u - x = -1 \quad \text{and} \quad x \equiv -u^2 \pmod{p} \quad (3)$$

From (2) and (3), we have that

$$u^2 - u + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \quad \text{and} \quad u^2 + u + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

respectively.

Conversely, suppose that $u^2 \pm u + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Clearly, we have the triangle

$$\infty \rightarrow \frac{u}{p} \rightarrow \frac{u \pm 1}{p} \rightarrow \infty$$

from Theorem 3.1.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Akbas, *On suborbital graphs for the modular group*, Bull. London Math. Soc. 33, no. 6, 2001, pp 647–652.
- [2] M. Akbas and T. Başkan, *Suborbital graphs for the normalizer of $\Gamma_0(N)$* , Tr. J. of Mathematics 20, 1996, pp 379–387.

- [3] N.L. Bigg and A.T. White, *Permutation groups and combinatorial structures*, London Mathematical Society Lecture Note Series 33, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1979.
- [4] G.A. Jones, D. Singerman, K. Wicks, *The Modular Group and Generalized Farey Graphs*, London Math. Soc. Lecture Note Series, Vol. 160, Cambridge University Press, 1991, pp 316–338.
- [5] R. S. Kulkarni, *An Arithmetic-Geometric Method in The Study of The Subgroups of The Modular Group*, American Journal of Mathematics, 113, 1991, pp 1053–1133.
- [6] B. Schoeneberg, *Elliptic Modular Functions*, Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1974.
- [7] C. C. Sims, *Graphs and Finite Permutation Groups*, Math. Z., 95, 1967, pp 76–86.
- [8] T. Tsuzuku, *Finite Groups and Finite Geometries*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1982.